

Combined use of untreated-waste rice husk ash and foundry sand waste in high-performance self-consolidating concrete

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Abstract

High-performance self-consolidating concrete (SCC) has great potential for advanced applications in modern concrete construction. SCC has high-performance characteristics especially high flow when in its fluid state it is poured into complicated molds and passes congested reinforcing steel without either excessive segregation or bleeding. Thus, SCC can develop strong early- and long-term mechanical and durability properties. The focus of this study is the combined effects of using foundry sand waste (FDW) obtained from the process of casting automobile engine parts as a fine aggregate replacement for Type-I Portland cement (OPC) in the amounts of 30 and 50 wt% with untreated rice husk ash (RHA) obtained from a rice husk-based fuel electricity power plant to replace OPC in the amounts of 10 and 20 wt%. The SCC prepared with water-binder materials (OPC and/or RHA) at a ratio (w/b) of 0.35 and 0.45 and the targeted slump flow in SCC production (the measured slump flow must be in the range of 70.0 ± 2.5 cm). In this study, a comprehensive investigation is undertaken that includes tests to determine the SCC specimens' fresh, hardened, and durability properties. The results indicate that FDW used to replace OPC to the extent specified has a positive effect on the SCC with RHA, increases the required superplasticizer amount and setting times compared to those of the control SCC, and decreases the slump flow of SCC. The incorporation of RHA and FDW decreases the filling, passing ability, and segregation of SCC while increasing its durability. In summary, with 10 wt% RHA together with 30 wt% FDW, the RHA-FDW-SCC produced showed the highest compressive and splitting tensile strengths of all the specimens tested compared to conventional SCC and met the durability requirements for SCC.

Keywords: Self-consolidating concrete; Foundry sand waste; Rice husk ash; Fresh-state properties; Mechanical properties; Durability properties

1. Introduction

Self-consolidating concrete (SCC) has been shown to achieve the fresh- and hardened-state requirements for modern concrete construction [1-4]. The American Concrete Institute (ACI) defines SCC as concrete that is highly flowable without segregation that can self-fill complicated or congested-reinforcing steel formwork with very little mechanical-forced consolidation [5]. However, a disadvantage of SCC is that a large amount of powder material is needed for lubrication and for generating fluid, which causes significant autogenous shrinkage. Additionally, the high pure-cement content in conventional SCC increases the already high temperature from the hydration reaction and causes thermal cracking in the concrete structure, which undermines the long-term durability of concrete [3,4]. The negative effects can be resolved by using pozzolan materials such as fly ash, silica fume, or meta-kaolin. In addition to reducing the cement content, the inclusion of pozzolan materials in SCC can improve the early- and late-stage compressive strength and decrease the water permeability of SCC. A potential material to use as a cement replacement in order to realize these improvements is rice husk ash (RHA).

A valuable byproduct of the process of burning rice husk/hull to produce electricity, RHA can be included in the composition of SCC [6]. For instance, Memon et al. [7] investigated the potential of RHA as a viscosity-modifying agent in producing SCC and considered the relative material costs. It has been found that most RHA particles used at 5 and 10 wt% of 500 kg-cement pass through a 150 μm sieve and that a specimen prepared with 10 wt% RHA and 4% superplasticizer agent (1) satisfies the European Federation of Specialist Construction Chemicals and Concrete Systems (EFNARC) requirements [8] and (2) due to dense particle packing and a decreasing w/b ratio has greater compressive strength than does conventional SCC. The cost of materials used compared to those needed to produce conventional SCC indicates 37.3%. In addition, Sua-iam and Makul [9] studied untreated RHA obtained from different combustion systems with a focus on particle size and loss on ignition. It was found that a high volume of RHA used as a partial replacement for fine aggregate at 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100% based on a target slump flow of 70.0 ± 2.5 cm in diameter reduced the compressive strength of the SCC produced in comparison with that of standard SCC by the increase of the water requirement of the SCC. RHA usually comprises up to 25% of the composition of SCC, which meets EFNARC's workability criteria [8] and

the Building Code Requirements for compressive strength [10]. The SCC described in [9] achieved compressive strength in the range of 28–35 MPa. However, RHA as a replacement for fine aggregate did not decrease the cost of producing concrete. Moreover, it may be possible to increase the RHA volume in SCC by using fine filler materials containing RHA. The use of filler may improve the fresh and hardened properties of SCC without increasing the cost of production such as grinding process [11,12]. In relation to RHA used as a replacement material in SCC, the performance and cost of SCC must be taken into account. It should also be noted that FDW has potential as a replacement for fine aggregate [13,14]. The effects of fine and coarse aggregates on the properties of SCC should be considered given that in the production of most SCC the quality and quantity of fine aggregate are of great importance in controlling its behavior. Because of the shortage of fine aggregate, e.g., natural sand, the possibility of recycling FDW as a replacement for fine aggregate (river sand) is investigated in this study [15,16].

FDW is a major by-product of the casting process of automobile inner-engine parts. Usually finer than original foundry sand, FDW is categorized as chemically bonded sand and is composed, for example, of 93.2% sand, 4.5% resin, 2.1% hexamine, and 0.2% calcium oxide [17-19]. In some studies, researchers have investigated the effect of FDW on the properties of concrete for uses such as filler or embankments [20,21]. It has been shown that FDW can be utilized as a fine aggregate replacement [22-23]. For example, Pathak and Siddique [14] used spent foundry sand at 10 wt% replacement in sand and heated the normal concrete specimen at a high temperature. The researchers found very little improvement in compressive strength although the amount of viscosity-modifying admixture needed decreased. However, to date, the literature has lacked research into the use of FDW in the production of SCC.

With highly porous RHA particles, RHA-mixed SCC has limitations in practical production and use. The incorporation of FDW may affect the properties of SCC in both fresh and hardened states. Given that these issues have not been thoroughly investigated, they are the defining focus of the present study. The use of RHA has the potential to render significant improvements in SCC, to make productive use of what are currently waste products, and to thereby produce an environmentally friendly concrete with all the properties required in the construction industry. In this study, RHA is used as a replacement material for cement and FDW as a replacement for fine aggregate (30 and 50 wt%) in the production of SCC. As noted, RHA is used in ordinary Portland cement (OPC) in limited amounts of 10 and 20 wt%, whereas FDW can fill the voids caused by the RHA particles. SCC prepared with water and

binder materials (OPC and/or RHA) controlled the w/b ratios of 0.35 and 0.45 and the targeted slump flow in SCC production (the measured slump flow must be at least in the range of 70.0 ± 2.5 cm to study the properties of fresh state (density, filling ability, passing ability, and setting time), mechanical hardened state (compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, and modulus of elasticity), and durability (water permeability, chloride permeability, drying shrinkage, and expansion due to exposure to sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4)).

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The RHA was collected by dust collectors, which are similar in size and replicate the working mechanism of machines used for the same purpose at a local electric power plant in Thailand, which uses rice husk as the main fuel for operating boilers at a burning temperature of 870.0 ± 20.0 °C and driving generators to produce electricity. In the SCC mixtures with RHA, the RHA was untreated and used as received. This RHA had a high silicon oxide (SiO_2) content (91.45 ± 1.34 by mass %) as detected by X-ray fluorescence (XRF) (Table 1).

Moreover, the RHA particle size, 50% cumulative passing, was 22.31 ± 0.88 μm , which makes the RHA particles larger than the OPC particles, the latter of which measured 13.50 ± 0.39 μm . The specific surface area was measured using the Brunauer, Emmett, and Teller (BET) method, which showed that the RHA had a smaller specific surface area (292.11 ± 20.04 m^2/kg) as compared with that of the OPC particles (324.23 ± 14.02 m^2/kg).

Additionally, the dry density of RHA (571.37 ± 13.79 kg/m^3) is lower than the dry density of OPC ($1,595.12 \pm 23.15$ kg/m^3) due to the high porosity of the RHA particles (Fig. 2(b)). Also, the dry density of RHA is lower than that of FDW particles ($1,073.24 \pm 18.56$ kg/m^3) due to the greater compaction of the FDW is finer than RHA as compared to that of the RHA, which is consistent with the particle size distribution (Fig. 1).

In the present study, the FDW was obtained from the casting process used to produce automobile engine parts. It was used as a replacement for standard fine aggregate (river sand) at 30 and 50 wt% without being refined or treated in any way. The specific surface area of the FDW was 275.03 ± 18.11 m^2/kg .

[Insert Table 1]

[Insert Fig. 1]

The percentage cumulative passing distribution of each of OPC, RHA, and FDW was measured and analyzed using a particle size analyzer. The results show that the OPC, RHA, and FDW particles measured 0.1–403.2 μm , 0.7–91.1 μm , and 0.2–190.1 μm , respectively (Fig. 1). Compared with river sand, the smallest river sand particles remaining after sieving in accordance with ASTM C33/C33M–18 [24] measured 1.49×10^{-2} cm—i.e., larger than the FDW particles in the mixture with 50% cumulative passing of 23.85 ± 0.42 μm .

In regard to morphology, there are considerable differences between OPC, RHA, and FDW (Fig. 2). RHA particles have a smooth surface and a slightly irregular shape. And, in comparison with OPC particles, they are larger and more porous. The high porosity of RHA increases the superplasticizer needed to achieve the target flow of SCC. Compared with OPC particles, FDW particles are more irregular in shape similar to sand particles and are generally larger. Some larger FDW particles are actually accumulations of smaller particles.

[Insert Fig. 2]

2.2 Mix proportions and specimen preparation

To produce high-performance SCC, specific mixtures of SCC mixed with RHA and/or FDW were included in the study. First, the water-binder materials (OPC and/or RHA) with a w/b ratio of 0.35 or 0.45 were controlled with binder materials of 450 and 650 kg/m^3 respectively for each ratio. RHA was used to replace OPC at 10 and 20 wt%, whereas the FDW was used to replace fine aggregate at 30 and 50 wt%. In total, 28 SCC mixtures were designed and investigated (Table 2). The standard OPC was produced in Thailand with a specific gravity of 3.14 ± 0.02 , and its properties were in accordance with ASTM C150/C150M–12 [25]. The properties of the conventional SCC were compared with those of the RHA-containing SCC. The local coarse aggregate was crushed limestone rock, whose gradation complied with ASTM C33/C33M–18 [24]. The properties of the river sand used as fine aggregate were in accordance with the specifications set out in ASTM C33/C33M–18 [24]. The specific gravity of the crushed rock was 2.64, and the specific gravity of the river sand was 2.72. The chemical admixture, which served as a kind of superplasticizer (Type G), was in accordance with the specifications set out in ASTM C494/C494–17 [26] and had a solid content of 42.5 wt%. This admixture was used to control the target slump flow range at

70.0 ± 2.5 cm. All the SCC specimens were demolded at 23.5 ± 0.5 h after mixing and continuously cured in lime-saturated water at a controlled temperature of 25.0 ± 2.0 °C until test time. The specimens were subjected to testing to determine the following properties: workability (filling and passing), slump flow loss, setting time, and strength (compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, static modulus of elasticity).

[Insert Table 2]

2.3 Testing standards and methods

2.3.1 Properties of SCC in fresh state

In relation to the target slump flow for SCC (the measured slump flow must be at least in the range of 70.0 ± 2.5 cm), and its properties can be classified as either (1) filling ability, i.e., the SCC's ability to fill the mold under its gravitational weight as specified by ASTM C1611/C1611M-14 [27], or (2) passing ability, i.e., the ability to pass through congested reinforcing steel as specified by ASTM C1621/C1621M-17 [28]. Moreover, the V-funnel flow time [29] and unit weight were evaluated in accordance with ASTM C138/C138M-17a [30] and the setting time in accordance with ASTM C403/C403M-16 [31].

2.3.2 Mechanical properties of SCC in the hardened state

The SCC specimens were tested for compressive strength and splitting tensile strength at the age of 28 days using methods in accordance with ASTM C39/C39M-18 [32], ASTM C496/C496M-17 [33], and ASTM C469/C469M-14, [34]. Seven-hundred and fifty-six SCC specimens with a diameter of 15.2 cm and a height of 30.4 cm were created from 28 SCC mixtures. These specimens were then cast and cured continuously until the test time at 3, 7, 14, 28, 56, 90, 120, 150, and 180 days. The specimens were tested for compressive strength and for splitting tensile strength, each of which was determined by averaging three values. Moreover, the relationships between the compressive-splitting tensile strengths were calculated.

2.3.3 Durability of SCC

The water permeability of the SCC specimens was tested and calculated in accordance with EN 12390-8 [35]. Three specimens for each of the mix proportions described were tested

at 28 and 180 days after mixing by applying water pressure of 500.0 ± 10 kPa for 72.0 ± 0.5 h on the test area equal to a 7.50 cm diameter area at the center bottom surface of the specimens, which measured 15.0 cm long \times 15.0 cm width \times 15.0 cm high. After water pressure had been applied for mixing, the maximum depth of penetration of the SCC specimens was measured and determined according to the standard specified [35]. To evaluate chloride permeability, a rapid chloride permeability test (RCPT) was carried out as per ASTM C1202-19 [36]. Discs 10.0 cm diameter \times 5.0 mm thick taken from the specimens were cast and then cured continuously from 1 to 180 and tested at 28 and 180 days. To test for chloride permeability, each specimen was placed between the two compartments cells with the cathode part filled with a 3% NaCl solution and the anode part filled with a 0.3 normality NaOH solution. In addition, the drying shrinkage of the SCC specimens was tested in accordance with ASTM C596-18 [37] using the prismatic specimen 28.5 cm long \times 7.5 cm width \times 7.5 cm thick, and the longitudinal expansion due to sulfate attack (Na_2SO_4) was tested in compliance with ASTM C1012/C1012M-18b [38] with a concentration of 352 moles of sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) per m^3 (50 g/L). The SCC specimens were tested for drying shrinkage and expansion characteristics until 360 days by controlling the temperature at 25.0 ± 2.0 °C with a relative humidity of $60.0 \pm 5.0\%$.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Properties of SCC in the fresh state

3.1.1 Superplasticizer requirement to achieve the target flow slump of SCC

To achieve the target flow slump range of SCC (70.0 ± 2.5 cm), the superplasticizer requirement of each SCC mixture was determined (Table 3). Compared to the control SCC (45R0FDW0 and 65R0FDW0), an increase in OPC content of SCC increased the superplasticizer requirement from 5.4 to 11.9 liters per cubic meter of SCC, indicating that a higher OPC content requires more superplasticizer to OPC particles and create flowability. This behavior is similar for RHA-containing SCC at a w/b ratio of 0.35 or 0.45 because RHA is not as dense as OPC, which means higher volume of RHA powder is required.

Compared with the conventional SCC, the superplasticizer requirements of the 0.35-w/b SCC specimens 45R10FDW0 and 65R10FDW0 were 8.9 and 15.9 liters higher per cubic meter of SCC, respectively, whereas those of 45R20FDW0 and 65R20FDW0 were 10.0 and

18.2 liters higher per cubic meter of SCC, respectively. However, when the w/b increased from 0.35 to 0.45, the requirement decreased (45R10FDW0) from 8.9 to 7.7 liters per cubic meter of SCC because the higher water content increased the workability of the SCC. The superplasticizer demand of the 65R10FDW0 specimen (decreased 0.27%) was lower than that of 45R10FDW0 (decreased 0.13%), and the 45R20FDW0 and 65R20FDW0 specimens showed an identical pattern.

In regard to the effect of FDW on the superplasticizer requirement, replacing fine aggregate with FDW had the effect of increasing the superplasticizer requirement in comparison with that of the control SCC and the RHA-mixed SCC. This difference is attributable to the higher specific surface area and greater density of the FDW as compared to the specific surface area and density of the RHA particles. Of the specimens tested, the increase in the superplasticizer requirement was most significant at an FDW replacement ratio of 50 wt%: given the greater FDW content and the lower density of FDW compared with river sand, the mixture would have high volume of FDW particles. Therefore, the SCC that includes FDW in its composition requires a higher dosage of superplasticizer than does the SCC in which FDW is not included. This was the case because compared with the specimen with a w/b ratio of 0.35 and the specimen with a w/b ratio of 0.45, the SCC that included FDW had a greater proportion of finer particles of FDW, which required a larger quantity of water.

[Insert Table 3]

3.1.2 Density

In terms of the density measurements of the fresh SCC mixtures with RHA and/or FDW, it is evident that in comparison with the control SCC an increased amount of RHA results in a lower density in the fresh state because RHA particles are not as dense as OPC particles: the 45R10FDW0 specimen has a density of 0.45 % and the 45R20FDW0 0.90 % that of conventional SCC (Table 3). However, SCC in which FDW was used as a replacement for fine aggregate was not as dense as conventional SCC. For example, 45R10FDW30 and 45R10FDW50 were 1.55 and 1.56 %, respectively, less dense than conventional SCC 1.56 % less dense.

For the SCC containing RHA and FDW, the density in the fresh state decreased as the proportion of FDW increased. Thus, FDW combined with fine aggregate has a stronger effect on density in the fresh state than does either replacing fine aggregate only with FDW or

replacing fine aggregate only with RHA in OPC. In regard to replacing fine aggregate with RHA in OPC, when the binder material content increased from 450 to 650 kg/m³, the mixture was not as dense in the fresh state as was the case for conventional SCC.

3.1.3 Filling ability

As noted, the SCC was designed to have a target slump flow in the range of 70.0 ± 2.5 cm. Filling ability was evaluated using the V-funnel flow time in accordance with EFNARC. The conventional SCC specimens 45R0FDW0 and 65R0FDW0 took 9 ± 0.2 and 7 ± 0.2 s, respectively (Table 3).

When RHA was included in SCC, the V-funnel flow time increased as more RHA particles are absorbed (Table 3). For example, the flow time increased from 9 ± 0.2 s to 11 ± 0.3 s (45R10FDW0) and 12 ± 0.3 s (45R20FDW0). However, when the binder materials increased to 650 kg/m³, the flow time decreased. Although RHA, OPC had a higher content to overcome the friction between the OPC-OPC, OPC-RHA, and RHA-RHA particles. In addition, the use of FDW to replace fine aggregate had a significant effect on flow time. Compared with the conventional SCC, the RHA-SCC specimen with FDW increased the flow time by approximately 2.0 and 1.5 times for 450 and 650 kg/m³ on average, respectively.

3.1.4 Passing ability

To evaluate the passing ability of SCC, as specified in ASTM C1621/C1621M–17 [28], a J-ring test was performed (Table 3). As expected based on the meticulous design of this study, the conventional SCC showed no visible blocking for either 450 or 650 kg/m³. However, for SCC that included RHA in its composition, noticeable blocking occurred, particularly at a binder materials content of 450 kg/m³ and a 0.35-w/b in the SCC specimen with 10 wt% of RHA. As expected, compared with OPC particles, RHA particles absorbed more water, which rendered the SCC-RHA relatively hard such that it did not flow across the obstructed iron bars (J-ring apparatus). However, with an increased binder content of 650 kg/m³, there was no occurrence for noticeable blocking of the SCC mixture prepared by 10 and 20 wt% RHA due to the increasing OPC content, as observed from the remaining amount of OPC of the 45R20FDW0 and 65R20FDW0, which were 360 and 520 kg/m³. This result suggests that when RHA is included in the composition of SCC, an OPC content of 520 kg/m³ or more should be specified.

In regard to the specimens with RHA (50 wt%) and FDW, extreme blocking occurred at a binder content of 450 kg/m³ because these specimens included particles that were even finer than standard fine aggregate, which indicates that the fresh SCC mix collapsed and was more condensed to agglomerates, or a high content because of the low mobility of SCC. However, at 650 kg/m³, no extreme blocking occurred despite the inclusion of FDW with high OPC content.

The segregation resistance of SCC prepared with w/b of 0.35 or w/b of 0.45 and a binder material content of 450 or 650 kg/m³ was evaluated (Table 3). It can be seen that the standard tests for the flowing and compacting characteristics of SCC—such as a slump flow test and a V-funnel test—are not sufficient to show segregation properties especially when applied to high-flow or low-viscosity SCC. Instead, results of funnel velocity (10/t_v) and J-ring tests are used to determine the segregation property of SCC and are plotted accordingly [39]. As expected, some SCC specimens that did not show segregation (Eq. (1)), whereas others did show segregation (Eq. (2)). For no segregation to take place, the SCC should be based on the J-ring test results ranging from 66.0–71.0 cm with funnel speed in the range of 0.83-1.67 s⁻¹:

$$y = (2 \times 10^{-17})x^{9.08}; R^2 = 0.6172 \text{ to achieve non-segregating SCC} \quad (1)$$

$$y = (2 \times 10^{-9})x^{4.70}; R^2 = 0.8827 \text{ to achieve segregating SCC} \quad (2)$$

[Insert Fig. 3]

3.1.5 Setting time

The initial and final setting times of SCC specimens with/without RHA or FDW for (a) 0.35-w/b and (b) 0.45-w/b were investigated (Table 3). For the conventional SCC (Fig. 6 (a)), the setting times of SCC decreased with increasing OPC content as a result of the rapid hydration reaction rate of OPC. Nevertheless, when RHA was used in OPC, the setting times of the SCC specimens increased due to the initially slow pozzolanic reaction of RHA in the early stage [12]. The setting times of the SCC specimens with FDW also increased because of the latter's inert-SiO₂ [18]. In addition, the water absorption of the finest FDW affected the internal structure formation of the calcium-silicate-hydrate (C-S-H) gel of the OPC. This phenomenon was also evident for SCC with 0.45-w/b.

3.2 Mechanical properties of SCC in the hardened state

3.2.1 Compressive strength

The results of averaging the compressive strength test results for SCC throughout the 180-day period are reported in this section (Figs. 4 and 5). Fig. 4 shows the SCC with binder materials content of 450 kg/m^3 , and Fig. 5 shows the SCC with binder materials content of 650 kg/m^3 . The compressive strength of the conventional SCC, SCC with RHA, and SCC with RHA and FDW increased continuously at a high rate in the early stage and decreased after 90 days due to the decreasing amount of unhydrated OPC, which resulted in decreased C-S-H at later ages. For the SCC specimens with 20 wt% RHA [40-42] or 10 wt% RHA with 30 wt% FDW, the compressive strength was higher than that of the conventional SCC because at 20 wt% RHA has the effect of an additional pozzolanic reaction. This result is consistent with the pozzolanicity test results from Chapelle's method [43] equal to $689.41 \pm 10.21 \text{ mg CaO/g sample}$, which resulted in increased additional C-S-H and strength in the SCC. For the SCC mixture with 10 wt% RHA together with 30 wt% FDW, the highest level of compressive strength was achieved as a result of the pozzolanic reaction arising from RHA associated with a greater filling effect of the finest FDW particles as compared with RHA particles. The finest FDW particles served as filler and densified the capillary pores within the RHA particles for SCC-RHA. However, this filling effect at 10 wt% RHA can enhance compressive strength to a greater extent than is the case for 20 wt% RHA. That is, too much filling from FDW impedes the formation of C-S-H gel such that the SCC specimen with 20 wt% RHA and 10 wt% FDW and the specimen with 20 wt% RHA and 30 and 50 wt% FDW developed less compressive strength than did the conventional SCC. For a binder materials content of 650 kg/m^3 , the compressive strength development of SCC as similar to the cases of SCC mixture prepared with 450 kg/m^3 binder materials content.

[Insert Fig. 4]

[Insert Fig. 5]

3.2.2 Splitting tensile strength

The splitting tensile strength of SCC prepared with (a) $w/b = 0.35$ and a binder material content of 450 kg/m^3 and (b) $w/b = 0.45$ and 650 kg/m^3 and a binder material content were considered (Figs. 6 and 7). In general, the splitting tensile strength development trend throughout the 180-day curing period was similar to the compressive strength development of

the SCC prepared with 10 wt% RHA and 30 wt% FDW. It should be noted that an increase in FDW leads to a slight decrease in splitting tensile strength. This decrease in splitting strength is attributable to the higher proportion of the FDW given that the latter's fine particles hinder the development of bond-strength in the interfacial transition zone between the OPC paste and the aggregate, which is associated, in turn, with the increased superplasticizer requirement of the SCC specimens [44].

The 28-day splitting tensile strength (y) and 28-day compressive strength (x) increase and can be plotted with the binder materials content (Fig. 8 (a)) and w/b (Fig. 8(b)) as shown in Eqs. (3)–(6) as follows:

$$y = 0.115x^{1.00}; \quad R^2 = 0.9973 \text{ for } 450 \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad (3)$$

$$y = 0.090x^{1.03}; \quad R^2 = 0.9881 \text{ for } 650 \text{ kg/m}^3 \quad (4)$$

$$y = 0.162x^{0.89}; \quad R^2 = 0.9688 \text{ for } w/b = 0.35 \quad (5)$$

$$y = 0.163x^{0.89}; \quad R^2 = 0.9731 \text{ for } w/b = 0.45 \quad (6)$$

[Insert Fig. 6]

[Insert Fig. 7]

[Insert Fig. 8]

3.2.3 Modulus of elasticity

The static modulus of elasticity of each SCC specimen was investigated (Fig. 8). This property is an important indicator of the stiffness of SCC together with the matrix phase, aggregate phase, and interfacial transition zone. Also, it is well-known that this property is closely related to the strength and internal pore structure of SCC [45,46]. The results show that the elastic modulus trend for the SCC is similar to the compressive strength development trend of SCC. The SCC specimens mixed with 10 wt% RHA incorporating 30 wt% FDW for the binder materials content of 450 or 650 kg/m³ were determined to be very good quality. Similar to compressive strength development, for the SCC specimen with FDW at more than 30 wt%, a significant decrease in compressive strength was noticed as stated earlier.

[Insert Fig. 9]

3.3 Durability of SCC

3.3.1 Water permeability

Water permeability is an important property governing the flow rate of water in the internal structure of SCC and is an indicator of the extent to which SCC can resist chemical attack, hot and cold weather, and so on. This property is affected by the size and connectivity of the gel and capillary pores [47] and can be represented as the water permeability coefficient (k). The water permeability coefficients of the SCC specimens at 28 and 180 days were determined (Table 4). It can be seen that the k values of conventional SCC at $w/b = 0.35$ are $44.82 \pm 2.31 (\times 10^{-12} \text{ m/s})$ at 28 days and $16.25 \pm 0.23 (\times 10^{-12} \text{ m/s})$ at 180 days, and $45.13 \pm 3.34 (\times 10^{-12} \text{ m/s})$ at 28 days and $18.54 \pm 0.53 (\times 10^{-12} \text{ m/s})$ at 180 days for SCC at $w/b = 0.35$. In general, the k values of SCC decreased with increasing curing time during increasing C-S-H gel filling in the gel and capillary pores. For the SCC with 10 wt% or 20 wt% RHA, the k values slightly decreased because the high porosity of the RHA particles enhances the absorption of the water molecules. The same phenomenon took place in the SCC specimens with a binder materials content of 650 kg/m^3 , although for these specimens less water was absorbed given that they had a high proportion of C-S-H gel from the hydration reaction of the cement. Also, 10 wt% RHA-SCC mixtures mixed without 30 wt% FDW had lower k values, which arose from the finest FDW particles in the range of $1.2\text{--}9.5 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. However, for the SCC with 20 wt% RHA without FDW and the SCC with 20 wt% RHA and 30 or 50% FDW, the k values increased due to the high porosity of RHA. For these specimens, the k values decreased slightly at 180 days compared to before this point due to the pozzolanic reaction of RHA.

[Insert Table 4]

3.2.2 Chloride permeability

In addition to water permeability, chloride permeability is considered in determining resistance to chloride penetration, as chloride ions can cause reinforcing steel embedded in concrete to rust. The chloride levels of SCC specimens show a tendency similar to the k values (Table 4). For instance, in terms of electrical charge, the conventional SCC specimens

had $1,579 \pm 15$ coulombs at 28 days and 626 ± 7 coulombs at 180 days for 45R0FDW0 prepared with w/b of 0.35. In compliance with ASTM C1202-19, which requires an evaluation of chloride ion penetrability to be based on the charge passed [36], 45R0FDW0 can be classified as having low chloride permeability at 28 days (1,000–2,000 coulombs) and very low permeability at 180 days (100–1,000 coulombs). Compared with the conventional SCC specimens, the 20 wt% RHA-SCC mixtures with/without FDW passed more coulombs due to the highly porous nature of RHA particles.

In regard to the specimens with 50 wt% FDW and 20 wt% RHA with a w/b of 0.35 and a binder materials content of 450 kg/m^3 , chloride permeability increased compared to conventional SCC due to the large pores of the RHA particles, which affected the pore content of the internal structure of the SCC specimens but could be classified as low chloride permeability (1,000–2,000 coulombs). However, for the SCC specimen with 10 wt% RHA, the FDW decreased the chloride permeability—an effect that arose from the finest FDW particles filling the internal structure thereby producing a SCC specimen with a very strong structure [48,49].

3.3.3 Drying shrinkage

Certainly, the drying shrinkage of SCC is a result of a loss of water molecules from within the SCC specimens due to the high temperature and low relative humidity of the surroundings and the water consumption entailed by the hydration and/or pozzolanic reaction. In general, the SCC specimens were similar in terms of shrinkage; that is, at the early stage of curing in the chamber, where temperature and relative humidity are controlled, the drying shrinkage increased with a high rate of shrinkage (Figs. 10 and 11). This is because at this stage the internal structure of the SCC specimens had a lot of water and capillary pores, which also had a large quantity of water, which can be moved out from the specimen especially during days 21 to 56 of curing. However, during the later stage from 90 to 180 days the drying shrinkage was constant due to an increasingly dense internal structure as the increased proportion of C-S-H gel had the effect of decreasing the number and size of the capillary pores.

In terms of the drying shrinkage of the binder materials content of 450 kg/m^3 and w/b = 0.35 (Fig. 10(a)), only the 45R10FDW0 and 45R10FDW30 mixtures showed less shrinkage than did the conventional SCC (45R0FDW0). This was the case because the pozzolanic reaction of the RHA and the filler effect of the finest FDW particles, which resulted in a densified internal structure: the number and size of the capillary pores were associated with

the dis-connectivity of the pores in the SCC specimens. This phenomenon gives rise to the opposite effect with an increasing amount of RHA and lower connecting-bond strength of the matrix phase and aggregate phases due to the addition of FDW [22]. In addition, the same behavior is evident in the SCC specimens with a binder materials content of 650 kg/m^3 and w/b of 0.45.

[Insert Fig. 10]

[Insert Fig. 11]

3.3.4 SCC Expansion due to sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) attack

SCC expands as a result of external sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) with a concentration of 352 moles of per m^3 (50 g/L) [38]. This causes spalling, cracking, and other signs of deterioration as an effect of calcium sulphate ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) or gypsum formation, which is greater than the volume of the sum of its components. Thus, internal pressure is generated, which, in turn, gives rise to cracks in the SCC. Figs. 12 and 13 show the changes in the expansion of SCC. Fig. 12 shows these changes in SCC prepared with w/b of 0.35 and binder materials content of (a) 450 kg/m^3 and (b) 650 kg/m^3 , and Fig. 13 shows SCC prepared with w/b of 0.45 and binder materials content of (a) 450 kg/m^3 and (b) 650 kg/m^3 . It can be seen that in general the extent to which the SCC specimens expand increases significantly and continuously at the early state (150 days first) and then slightly decreases until reaching constant expansion to 360 days. An important factor in early-stage expansion is the internal structure of the SCC specimens, which are replete with water molecules and have a high number of capillary pores. The sulphate ion (SO_4^{2-}) can react with hydrated calcium aluminate ($3\text{CaO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$), thereby producing ettringite (calcium sulphoaluminate hydrate $\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12} \cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$), and with calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$), thereby producing gypsum. Especially during days 120–150 of immersion, the expansion rates of the SCC specimens are highest, next to decreasing until approaching a constant low rate as the proportion of C-S-H gel increases.

Only the 45R10FDW0 and 45R10FDW30 mixtures showed less shrinkage than did the conventional SCC mixture (45R0FDW0), due to the densification of the internal structure of the SCC specimens. Other SCC specimens showed opposite results because of the high porosity of the RHA particles and weakening bonding of FDW [18].

[Insert Fig. 12]

[Insert Fig. 13]

4. Usability, economic savings and environmental aspects

To successfully use the by-products RHA and FDW in the production of SCC, it is necessary to meet set codes and standards [5,8]. Further, it is necessary to take the following points into consideration:

- It is important to understand the nature of RHA and FDW. RHA is usually obtained from an electric power plant that uses only rice husk/hull as fuel in the burning process such as circulating fluidized bed combustion. Through this process, amorphous RHA is produced at an incinerating temperature between 550 and 700 °C for 1 hour [41,42]) and supporting by-effective control system. Therefore, the effect on the basic properties of the RHA must be controlled, including its mechanical properties, durability, chemical composition, and physical properties. Similarly, in regard to using FDW, some of its characteristics are influenced by the various properties of original foundry sand and the automobile engine-part casting process. Here, the durability of FDW is significant in ensuring the long-term performance of SCC applications. In particular, the durability of the FDW depends on the relative purity of the sand used in the foundry process. Subjected to continuous forming and demolding with the pouring of melted metal, FDW may deteriorate because of temperature shock/runaway. Moreover, at the later stage in the manufacture of core parts, the original sand particles and their properties may deteriorate at an accelerated rate. However, in SCC engineering applications, FDW is not typically subjected to severe conditions. Therefore, FDW can easily be used in ways that conform to the specifications of industry bodies provided that suppliers of the original foundry sand certify its quality. It should be noted, too, that FDW is ordinarily stored outside the factories where it is produced such that it is exposed to changing temperature and moisture conditions. For this reason, FDW should be collected from the factories using a dust collector and subjected to a thorough screening process.

- Economic savings are an indicator of the success of RHA and FDW used in SCC, and the extent to which savings are possible depends on the cost of preparation and the relative availability of RHA and FDW coupled with the relative availability of natural aggregate in the region. The economic viability of using RHA and FDW is greater when used at ready-mixed concrete plants and precast concrete yards as compared to other contexts.

- Environmental aspects of using RHA and FDW pertain to controlling the leachate from RHA and FDW, which may contain hazardous trace concentrations exceeding primary quality standards for consumption. However, these concentrations are the same as than other concrete materials. Thus, it is necessary for governmental agencies charged with protecting the environment to oversee suppliers of RHA and FDW in order to maintain the quality of the water supply, which can be achieved through mechanical methods, e.g., compacting and grading to minimize leachate.

5. Conclusions

Based on the use of FDW as a replacement for fine aggregate at 30 and 50 wt% and based on the properties of SCC with RHA used as a replacement for OPC at 10 or 20 wt%, the following conclusions are drawn:

- To achieve the target flow slump for SCC (70.0 ± 2.5 cm), FDW used to replace fine aggregate at up to 50 wt% increases the superplasticizer requirement more than either conventional SCC or SCC with RHA. At this replacement amount, too, the use of FDW decreases density in the fresh state as compared to the density of fresh-state conventional SCC. In addition, density in the fresh state for SCC containing both RHA and FDW decreases further as FDW in amounts over 50 wt% replacement is used.

- The use of FDW increases the V-funnel flow time considerably. The RHA-SCC specimen containing FDW shows increased flow time, and the setting times of SCC with increasing FDW because of the inert-SiO₂ of FDW. Moreover, at a binder content of 450 kg/m³ and 0.35-w/b, the SCC with 10 wt% RHA showed blocking, whereas the specimens at 650 kg/m³ with 10 or 20 wt% RHA did not have noticeable blocking.

- The 10% RHA-SCC specimen with 30 wt% FDW achieved the highest compressive strength, splitting tensile strength, and static modulus of elasticity. This specimen also showed higher compressive and splitting tensile strength than did the conventional SCC.

- For the SCC specimens with fine aggregate replaced with FDW at 10 or 20 wt% the water permeability coefficient k values decreased slightly. Further, the FDW decreased the chloride permeability of these specimens. Moreover, at the early stage, the drying shrinkage increased with a high rate of shrinking. However, the specimen with fine aggregate replaced with RHA without FDW at 10 wt% and the specimen with 10 wt% RHA associated with 30

wt% FDW mixtures showed less shrinkage than did the conventional SCC consistent with the expansion results under sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) attack.

- Based on the environmental aspects, the utilization of RHA and FDW as raw materials in the production of SCC can help to reduce the landfill leachate from RHA and FDW, which may contain hazardous trace concentrations exceeding the water quality standard for human consumption.

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Tables

Table 1 Chemical composition and physical properties of OPC, RHA, and FDW.

Chemical composition	OPC	RHA	FDW
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(by mass, %)	(Mean \pm SD ^[1])	(Mean \pm SD)	(Mean \pm SD)
SiO ₂	19.84 \pm 0.52	91.45 \pm 1.34	82.19 \pm 1.24
Al ₂ O ₃	4.21 \pm 0.28	0.44 \pm 0.06	4.76 \pm 0.31
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.19 \pm 0.09	0.18 \pm 0.02	2.63 \pm 0.28
MgO	1.25 \pm 0.02	0.36 \pm 0.20	0.77 \pm 0.08
CaO	68.02 \pm 1.06	0.99 \pm 0.07	1.34 \pm 0.42
Na ₂ O	0.18 \pm 0.03	0.11 \pm 0.02	0.75 \pm 0.04
K ₂ O	0.33 \pm 0.06	1.39 \pm 0.03	0.59 \pm 0.09
SO ₃	1.59 \pm 0.17	0.04 \pm 0.02	0.03 \pm 0.01
Loss on ignition	0.92 \pm 0.04	1.39 \pm 0.03	3.63 \pm 0.19
Physical properties	OPC (Mean \pm SD)	RHA (Mean \pm SD)	FDW (Mean \pm SD)
Particle size at 50% cumulative passing (μ m)	13.50 \pm 0.39	22.31 \pm 0.88	23.85 \pm 0.42
Specific gravity	3.14 \pm 0.02	2.32 \pm 0.05	2.42 \pm 0.01
Specific surface area (m ² /kg)	324.23 \pm 14.02	292.11 \pm 20.04	275.03 \pm 18.1
Density (kg/m ³)	1,595.12 \pm 23.15	571.37 \pm 13.79	1,073.24 \pm 18.56
Pozzolanicity (Chapelle (mg CaO/g sample))	Not Applicable	689.41 \pm 10.21	Not Applicable

Remark: ^[1] SD is the standard deviation of the test result.

Table 2 Mixture proportions of SCC.

SCC Type	w/b ratio	Binder materials (kg/m ³)	OPC (kg/m ³)	RHA (kg/m ³)	Sand (kg/m ³)	FDW (kg/m ³)	Crushed limestone rock (kg/m ³)	Water (kg/m ³)	Superplasticizer Type G [26] (liter/m ³)
45R0FDW0 ^[1]	0.35	450	450	0	1046	0	902	154.2	5.4 ± 0.26
45R10FDW0	0.35	450	405	45	1046	0	902	152.0	8.9 ± 0.31
45R20FDW0	0.35	450	360	90	1046	0	902	151.3	10.0 ± 0.34
45R10FDW30	0.35	450	405	45	732	314	902	147.7	15.8 ± 0.35
45R10FDW50	0.35	450	405	45	523	523	902	147.5	16.1 ± 0.37
45R20FDW30	0.35	450	360	90	732	314	902	147.3	16.4 ± 0.40
45R20FDW50	0.35	450	360	90	523	523	902	146.7	17.4 ± 0.42
45R0FDW0	0.45	450	450	0	1046	0	902	198.4	6.6 ± 0.21
45R10FDW0	0.45	450	405	45	1046	0	902	197.7	7.7 ± 0.33
45R20FDW0	0.45	450	360	90	1046	0	902	196.6	9.5 ± 0.36
45R10FDW30	0.45	450	405	45	732	314	902	195.9	10.6 ± 0.40
45R10FDW50	0.45	450	405	45	523	523	902	194.8	12.4 ± 0.43
45R20FDW30	0.45	450	360	90	732	314	902	193.8	14.1 ± 0.49
45R20FDW50	0.45	450	360	90	523	523	902	192.0	17.0 ± 0.51
65R0FDW0	0.35	650	650	0	961	0	828	220.1	11.9 ± 0.20
65R10FDW0	0.35	650	585	65	961	0	828	217.6	15.9 ± 0.23
65R20FDW0	0.35	650	520	130	961	0	828	216.2	18.2 ± 0.29
65R10FDW30	0.35	650	585	65	673	288	828	211.9	25.2 ± 0.31
65R10FDW50	0.35	650	585	65	481	481	828	211.2	26.3 ± 0.34
65R20FDW30	0.35	650	520	130	673	288	828	210.8	26.9 ± 0.49
65R20FDW50	0.35	650	520	130	481	481	828	210.3	27.8 ± 0.51
65R0FDW0	0.45	650	650	0	961	0	828	286.6	9.5 ± 0.19
65R10FDW0	0.45	650	585	65	961	0	828	285.5	11.3 ± 0.22
65R20FDW0	0.45	650	520	130	961	0	828	285.1	11.9 ± 0.25
65R10FDW30	0.45	650	585	65	673	288	828	283.3	14.8 ± 0.29
65R10FDW50	0.45	650	585	65	481	481	828	282.8	15.6 ± 0.31
65R20FDW30	0.45	650	520	130	673	288	828	282.1	16.8 ± 0.38
65R20FDW50	0.45	650	520	130	481	481	828	281.2	18.2 ± 0.39

Remarks: ^[1] XRYUZ denotes the following: X is the powder material content (OPC + RHA) (450 and 650 kg/m³), RY is the percentage OPC replacement of RHA content (0, 10 and 20 wt%), and FDWZ is the percentage sand replacement of foundry sand (FS) content (0, 30, and 50 wt%).

Table 3 Fresh-state properties of SCC.

Mixture labels	Slump flow	J-ring test	Difference	Blocking assessment ^[1]	V-funnel flow	Fresh density		Setting times	
	(cm)	(initial) (cm)	(initial) (cm)		time (s)	value (kg/m ³)	% conventional	Initial (min)	Final (min)
45R0FDW0 ^[1]	70 ± 0.3	68 ± 0.1	2 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	9 ± 0.2	2,384 ± 11	100 ± 0.02	117 ± 12	146 ± 15
45R10FDW0	71 ± 0.5	68 ± 0.1	3 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	11 ± 0.3	2,373 ± 9	-0.45 ± 0.08	132 ± 18	162 ± 10
45R20FDW0	71 ± 0.4	67 ± 0.2	4 ± 0.2	Noticeable blocking	12 ± 0.3	2,362 ± 12	-0.90 ± 0.06	144 ± 11	174 ± 16
45R10FDW30	72 ± 0.1	67 ± 0.4	5 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	14 ± 0.1	2,357 ± 14	-1.11 ± 0.05	158 ± 19	185 ± 11
45R10FDW50	72 ± 0.2	65 ± 0.5	7 ± 0.1	Extreme blocking	18 ± 0.2	2,347 ± 16	-1.55 ± 0.04	170 ± 10	198 ± 10
45R20FDW30	72 ± 0.6	63 ± 0.1	9 ± 0.2	Extreme blocking	22 ± 0.4	2,347 ± 10	-1.56 ± 0.02	174 ± 8	199 ± 19
45R20FDW50	72 ± 0.2	60 ± 0.1	12 ± 0.3	Extreme blocking	26 ± 0.5	2,336 ± 17	-2.00 ± 0.05	183 ± 12	218 ± 12
45R0FDW0	72 ± 0.4	70 ± 0.3	2 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	8 ± 0.2	2,349 ± 12	-1.47 ± 0.08	142 ± 7	178 ± 13
45R10FDW0	71 ± 0.1	69 ± 0.2	2 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	9 ± 0.3	2,338 ± 14	-1.92 ± 0.04	160 ± 5	198 ± 9
45R20FDW0	72 ± 0.4	69 ± 0.1	3 ± 0.2	Noticeable blocking	11 ± 0.1	2,327 ± 18	-2.37 ± 0.09	178 ± 10	215 ± 6
45R10FDW30	70 ± 0.1	66 ± 0.5	4 ± 0.2	Noticeable blocking	12 ± 0.2	2,322 ± 19	-2.58 ± 0.10	189 ± 11	224 ± 13
45R10FDW50	70 ± 0.2	65 ± 0.2	5 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	15 ± 0.4	2,312 ± 10	-3.02 ± 0.08	202 ± 12	236 ± 10
45R20FDW30	71 ± 0.2	65 ± 0.4	6 ± 0.1	Extreme blocking	18 ± 0.3	2,312 ± 9	-3.04 ± 0.02	205 ± 16	240 ± 12
45R20FDW50	72 ± 0.3	64 ± 0.2	8 ± 0.2	Extreme blocking	21 ± 0.2	2,301 ± 12	-3.48 ± 0.04	218 ± 7	258 ± 7
65R0FDW0	72 ± 0.4	70 ± 0.2	2 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	7 ± 0.2	2,454 ± 12	100 ± 0.02	103 ± 4	122 ± 10
65R10FDW0	72 ± 0.3	70 ± 0.3	2 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	9 ± 0.1	2,439 ± 10	-0.60 ± 0.06	115 ± 10	134 ± 12
65R20FDW0	72 ± 0.1	60 ± 0.3	10 ± 0.3	No visible blocking	10 ± 0.3	2,424 ± 8	-1.24 ± 0.08	124 ± 13	148 ± 16
65R10FDW30	71 ± 0.2	68 ± 0.4	3 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	12 ± 0.4	2,425 ± 12	-1.20 ± 0.06	139 ± 15	159 ± 11
65R10FDW50	72 ± 0.4	68 ± 0.2	4 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	14 ± 0.2	2,415 ± 14	-1.60 ± 0.04	152 ± 16	179 ± 4
65R20FDW30	71 ± 0.1	66 ± 0.5	5 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	16 ± 0.3	2,410 ± 16	-1.80 ± 0.02	155 ± 10	180 ± 3
65R20FDW50	70 ± 0.5	65 ± 0.1	5 ± 0.2	Noticeable blocking	20 ± 0.5	2,400 ± 12	-2.20 ± 0.06	168 ± 12	202 ± 7
65R0FDW0	72 ± 0.3	71 ± 0.2	1 ± 0.2	No visible blocking	6 ± 0.1	2,402 ± 13	-2.12 ± 0.07	128 ± 16	162 ± 10
65R10FDW0	71 ± 0.3	70 ± 0.2	1 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	7 ± 0.2	2,386 ± 9	-2.76 ± 0.03	149 ± 14	184 ± 12
65R20FDW0	70 ± 0.2	69 ± 0.3	1 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	8 ± 0.2	2,372 ± 10	-3.36 ± 0.02	165 ± 11	195 ± 10
65R10FDW30	72 ± 0.4	70 ± 0.4	2 ± 0.1	No visible blocking	9 ± 0.3	2,373 ± 14	-3.32 ± 0.10	176 ± 12	212 ± 16
65R10FDW50	72 ± 0.1	69 ± 0.5	3 ± 0.1	Noticeable blocking	10 ± 0.3	2,363 ± 13	-3.72 ± 0.13	192 ± 17	225 ± 18
65R20FDW30	71 ± 0.2	67 ± 0.3	4 ± 0.2	Noticeable blocking	13 ± 0.1	2,357 ± 12	-3.96 ± 0.09	195 ± 7	229 ± 11
65R20FDW50	71 ± 0.3	66 ± 0.1	5 ± 0.2	Noticeable blocking	14 ± 0.1	2,348 ± 18	-4.32 ± 0.08	212 ± 8	246 ± 16

Remark: ^[1] For the blocking assessment, the differences in slump flow and J-ring flow diameters were determined. In this assessment, 0–2.5 cm is defined as no visible blocking, 2.5–5.0 cm) as minimal to noticeable blocking, and greater than 5.0 cm as noticeable to extreme blocking.

Table 4 Hardened-state properties of the SCC mixes.

Mixture label	Water permeability coefficient, k [35]		Chloride permeability [36]	
	28 days ($\times 10^{-12}$ m/s)	180 days ($\times 10^{-12}$ m/s)	28 days (coulombs)	180 days (coulombs)
45R0FDW0	44.82 \pm 2.31	16.25 \pm 0.23	1,579 \pm 15	626 \pm 7
45R10FDW0	40.18 \pm 1.46	15.27 \pm 0.72	1,415 \pm 22	270 \pm 12
45R20FDW0	60.22 \pm 3.01	34.39 \pm 0.40	2,122 \pm 10	1,299 \pm 20
45R10FDW30	36.23 \pm 1.14	12.98 \pm 0.98	1,275 \pm 9	512 \pm 6
45R10FDW50	53.11 \pm 2.24	28.93 \pm 0.22	1,872 \pm 6	1,099 \pm 12
45R20FDW30	48.61 \pm 1.91	22.10 \pm 0.33	1,714 \pm 18	827 \pm 9
45R20FDW50	55.27 \pm 2.01	39.02 \pm 0.15	1,940 \pm 25	1,578 \pm 11
45R0FDW0	45.13 \pm 3.34	18.54 \pm 0.53	1,590 \pm 16	690 \pm 9
45R10FDW0	42.81 \pm 0.99	18.41 \pm 0.42	1,502 \pm 19	688 \pm 13
45R20FDW0	61.92 \pm 1.54	35.21 \pm 0.67	2,177 \pm 22	1,354 \pm 17
45R10FDW30	39.05 \pm 1.72	14.33 \pm 0.87	1,376 \pm 17	511 \pm 6
45R10FDW50	55.76 \pm 3.61	30.88 \pm 0.25	1,904 \pm 26	1,157 \pm 13
45R20FDW30	49.06 \pm 3.19	24.38 \pm 0.84	1,799 \pm 20	939 \pm 15
45R20FDW50	58.01 \pm 3.04	42.22 \pm 0.11	2,040 \pm 11	1,582 \pm 20
65R0FDW0	32.33 \pm 0.78	11.42 \pm 0.29	1,132 \pm 9	423 \pm 6
65R10FDW0	29.16 \pm 2.05	10.79 \pm 0.33	998 \pm 12	401 \pm 10
65R20FDW0	42.54 \pm 3.32	23.04 \pm 0.42	1,492 \pm 14	875 \pm 9
65R10FDW30	25.99 \pm 2.64	10.15 \pm 0.67	815 \pm 5	332 \pm 5
65R10FDW50	37.40 \pm 2.73	19.54 \pm 0.88	1,314 \pm 15	729 \pm 10
65R20FDW30	35.05 \pm 1.81	13.47 \pm 0.49	1,244 \pm 26	511 \pm 8
65R20FDW50	39.91 \pm 1.99	25.09 \pm 0.23	1,523 \pm 29	941 \pm 16
65R0FDW0	32.65 \pm 3.02	12.89 \pm 0.26	1,155 \pm 18	498 \pm 7
65R10FDW0	31.95 \pm 3.29	11.79 \pm 0.54	1,100 \pm 9	427 \pm 12
65R20FDW0	43.97 \pm 2.77	21.13 \pm 0.33	1,565 \pm 13	798 \pm 15
65R10FDW30	27.23 \pm 2.83	10.02 \pm 0.15	939 \pm 11	329 \pm 19
65R10FDW50	41.31 \pm 1.29	18.22 \pm 0.08	1,422 \pm 25	665 \pm 9
65R20FDW30	36.47 \pm 2.44	14.98 \pm 0.10	1,287 \pm 20	534 \pm 6
65R20FDW50	42.13 \pm 2.65	27.18 \pm 0.91	1,408 \pm 12	936 \pm 14

Figures

Fig. 1 Particle size distributions of OPC, FDW, and RHA in the semi-logarithmic scale.

Fig. 2 SEM micrographs (5000×) of (a) OPC, (b) RHA, and (c) FDW.

Fig. 3 Segregation in relation to the slump flow mass and funnel speed of SCC prepared with w/b of 0.35 and w/b of 0.45 and a binder materials content of 450 and 650 kg/m³.

Fig. 4 Compressive strength of SCC prepared with (a) $w/b = 0.35$ and (b) $w/b = 0.45$ and a binder materials content of 450 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 5 Compressive strength of SCC prepared with (a) $w/b = 0.35$ and (b) $w/b = 0.45$ and a binder materials content of 650 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 6 Splitting tensile strength of SCC prepared with (a) $w/b = 0.35$ and (b) $w/b = 0.45$ and a binder materials content of 450 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 7 Splitting tensile strength of SCC prepared with (a) $w/b = 0.35$ and (b) $w/b = 0.45$ and a binder materials content of 650 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 8 Relationship between the 28-day compressive strength and splitting tensile strength of SCC and the (a) binder materials content and (b) w/b of the SCC mixture.

Fig. 9 Modulus of elasticity of SCC prepared with w/b = 0.35 and w/b = 0.45 and binder materials content of 450 and 650 kg/m³.

Fig. 10 Drying shrinkage of SCC prepared with $w/b = 0.35$ and binder materials content of (a) 450 kg/m^3 and (b) 650 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 11 Drying shrinkage of SCC prepared with $w/b = 0.45$ and binder materials content of (a) 450 kg/m^3 and (b) 650 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 12 Expansion due to immersion in sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) with 352 moles per m^3 (50 g/L) of SCC prepared with $w/b = 0.35$ and binder materials content of (a) 450 kg/m^3 and (b) 650 kg/m^3 .

Fig. 13 Expansion due to immersion in sodium sulfate (Na_2SO_4) with 352 moles per m^3 (50 g/L) of SCC prepared with $w/b = 0.45$ and binder materials content of (a) 450 kg/m^3 and (b) 650 kg/m^3 .